

Social robots in Czech residential care services: Comparing the perspectives of social work students and workers in homes for the older people

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Abstract

The aim of our research was to explore and compare the perspectives of students of social work and workers of homes for older people on the use of social robots in homes for older people. In our research, we used the standardized UNRAQ questionnaire (Tobis et al. 2021). We distributed a modified questionnaire to (1) students of social work ($N = 140$) who had taken a gerontology course. We also distributed the questionnaire among (2) workers of homes for older people ($N = 133$) who had not received any training in gerontechnology to date. Subsequently, we organised a focus group with (14) students and interviews with (23) workers of homes for older people, including managers, social workers, direct-care workers, and health care workers. The quantitative data collected were evaluated using statistical procedures, and the qualitative data were subjected to thematic analysis. Students who were educated in gerontechnology accepted the use-potential of social robots in social work practice to a higher degree compared to workers who were not educated in this area. The research results showed that education in gerontechnology can play a key role in the adoption of social robots and their subsequent use in practice.

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Introduction

Social robots have been increasingly used in older adult care due to benefits in assisting physical, emotional, and social well-being. Social workers play a crucial role in working closely with other care professionals to ensure that the holistic needs of older adults are met. Most of the current research focuses on the acceptance and perceptions of robots among general care workers, and the findings are somewhat divergent depending on professional background and cultural differences (Niewrzol and Ostermann 2024). While the attitudes and intentions of social workers have been less well-researched, particularly in studies comparing the views of social work students with those of practitioners (Zhang, Luo, and Wang 2024). Exploring social workers' (both existing and future professionals) views on the use of robots in older adults care would inform the effective implementation of robots in practice. In this study, the research question was defined as: *What are the differences in the adoption of social robots between students of social work and workers in homes for older people, including perceived benefits and barriers?*

Social robots in older adults' care

In the Czech Republic, social workers specialising in work with older adults (gerontological social work) do not hold an officially recognised professional title or formally defined specialisation. Nevertheless, their role exists in practice and is commonly implemented. In residential social care services, their role typically involves supporting older adults during the process of adaptation to a new environment and coordinating care within a multidisciplinary team. Social workers collaborate with doctors, psychologists, occupational therapists, physiotherapists, and direct-care workers. Their primary goal is to ensure comprehensive and coordinated support for older people, based on the bio-psycho-social model (Engel 1977), which recognises the interaction of biological, psychological, and social factors.

The increasing use of robotic technology in older adult care requires involvement of all professional groups, such as nurses, occupational therapists, care managers, and social workers, to develop corresponding competencies. Research has shown that health and social care

professionals need a range of competencies to effectively use social robots, including basic skills like operating robots and managing malfunctions, as well as more advanced competencies in social and communication skills, along with ethical, legal, and security knowledge (Konttila et al. 2019; Papadopoulous et al. 2023). As the future workforce, the perspectives of healthcare students have also been examined in some studies. Their attitudes toward robots and their expectations are mixed [for example Kropińska et al. (2020) or van Kemenade, Hoorn, and Konijn (2019)].

Different stakeholder groups have varied expectations and concerns regarding the use of social robots. Caregivers prioritize safety and emergency notifications (Bedaf et al. 2018), whereas healthcare professionals view certain functionalities of robots, such as the ability to observe and record mental and physical conditions, as beneficial. Healthcare professionals, in particular, also emphasize the importance of robots in falls prevention and mobility support (Kodate et al. 2022). Meanwhile, care service managers may have reservations about the adaptability of robots in complex caregiving environments, though direct-care workers often hold more positive expectations regarding how robots can alleviate physically demanding tasks (Na, Jung, and Kim 2023).

As the submitted body of research on the adoption of social robots shows, there are distinctions between different professional and target groups. In view of the target group of older adults living in the Czech Republic in residential social services such as homes for older people (number of clients: 34,096) and homes with special care (number of clients: 22,840), we were interested in views of their workers and students of social work as future stakeholders in this field (Statistical Yearbook 2023). Considering the ageing population, these institutions will face staff shortages, for which the potential of social robots can be used.

Methodology

The aim of our research was to explore and compare the views of students of social work and workers of homes for older people on the use of social robots in these homes, focusing on their description of the benefits and barriers they identified. We formulated the research question: *What are the differences in the adoption of social robots between students of social work and workers in homes for older people, including perceived benefits and barriers?*

We used a mixed research strategy, specifically ‘Explanatory Design’ (Creswell and Clark 2007), which is a two-stage research design. In line with Creswell and Clark (2007), the first stage started with (1) quantitative research using a standardized Users’ Needs, Requirements, and Abilities Questionnaire (UNRAQ) designed by Tobis et al. (2021). The

particular UNRAQ domains are (A) interaction with the robot and technical issues (10 statements), (B) assistive role of the robot (13 statements), (C) social aspects of using the robot (6 statements), (D) ethical issues (5 statements). This questionnaire can be used to collect data on the use of social robots in older adult care from different target groups (older adults, formal and informal caregivers, and students of helping professions study programmes).

The UNRAQ questionnaire (see supplementary material) was distributed to undergraduate full-time social work students at two European universities ($N=140$, 100%), one university in the Czech Republic ($N=70$), and one university in Slovenia ($N=70$) that currently educate social work students in the field of gerontechnology. One hundred twenty-four (88%) were female and sixteen (12%) were male. The average student age was 20 years (min. 19, max. 28). Sixteen (11%) students indicated that they would like to work with a target group of older adults in the future, twenty-two (33%) indicated that they did not plan to work with this target group after their graduation, and thirty-seven (56%) indicated that they did not know yet.

The UNRAQ questionnaire was also distributed to workers in homes for older people in the Czech Republic. A total of sixteen homes for older people were contacted by email addressing all home directors in the city of Ostrava. A total of 133 completed questionnaires were received from the staff of homes for older people. The average age of the workers was 45 years (min. 20, max. 61). In terms of work position, 103 social service workers, 20 social workers, 4 social service managers, 3 activation workers, 1 occupational therapist, 1 general nurse, and 1 director were involved in the research. Descriptive statistics were used to analyse the quantitative data, providing a summary of the responses from both social work students and care workers. The results are presented in Tables 1–5.

Students and workers expressed their degree of agreement or disagreement on a five-point Likert scale (1 = I strongly agree, 2 = I tend to agree, 3 = I neither agree nor disagree, 4 = I tend to disagree, 5 = I strongly disagree) used throughout the questionnaire.

In the second stage of the research, we continued (2) with qualitative research, conducting focus group with Czech students of social work ($N=14$) and individual interviews with workers in homes for older people ($N=23$) in the Czech Republic. The interviews involved workers at different levels—directors (2), social workers (16), social service workers (3), and health care professionals (2). The interviews with staff lasted on average 36 minutes.

Although social work students from both the Czech Republic and Slovenia participated in the study, data collection among care workers was limited to the Czech Republic. Organisational barriers prevented access within the timeframe of this study. This limitation is acknowledged,

Table 1. Comparison of responses of students and workers in homes for older people by percentage of agreement.

Domain	Area	Students (1 = I strongly agree + 2 = I tend to agree)	Workers in homes for older people (1 = I strongly agree + 2 = I tend to agree)	Variance
Interaction with the robot and technical issues	A10	52%	53%	1%
Social aspects of using the robot	C5	52%	53%	1%
Assistive role of the robot	B13	71%	73%	2%
Interaction with the robot and technical issues	A4	19%	23%	4%
Interaction with the robot and technical issues	A2	54%	49%	5%
Social aspects of using the robot	C3	67%	62%	5%
Assistive role of the robot	B12	89%	83%	6%
Interaction with the robot and technical issues	A5	26%	20%	6%
Assistive role of the robot	B1	70%	63%	7%
Social aspects of using the robot	C4	81%	74%	7%
Assistive role of the robot	B11	69%	61%	8%
Ethical issues	D1	73%	65%	8%
Social aspects of using the robot	C1	81%	72%	9%
Social aspects of using the robot	C2	73%	64%	9%
Ethical issues	D3	57%	47%	10%
Ethical issues	D4	84%	73%	11%
Assistive role of the robot	B7	64%	53%	11%
Interaction with the robot and technical issues	A1	61%	50%	11%
Ethical issues	D2	77%	62%	15%
Assistive role of the robot	B4	61%	46%	15%
Ethical issues	D5	42%	27%	15%
Assistive role of the robot	B10	78%	62%	15%
Interaction with the robot and technical issues	A8	81%	65%	16%
Social aspects of using the robot	C6	63%	47%	16%
Assistive role of the robot	B5	72%	56%	17%

Source: Authors' own research.

as it restricts the potential for direct cross-national comparison of professional perspectives. These constraints are widely acknowledged as a limitation in cross-national comparative research in gerontological social work (Clark 2008).

Data collection took place between March 2022 and March 2024. We used elements of thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke 2012) to analyse the data.

Table 2. Comparison of student and worker in homes for older people ratings in the A domain *Interaction with the robot and technical issues.*

Domain	Area	Students						Workers in homes for older people					
		I agree		I neither agree nor disagree		I disagree		I agree		I neither agree nor disagree		I disagree	
		n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Interaction with the robot and technical issues	A1	85	61%	33	24%	22	16%	66	50%	30	23%	37	28%
	A2	75	54%	37	26%	28	20%	65	49%	35	26%	33	25%
	A3	95	68%	31	22%	14	10%	64	48%	36	27%	33	25%
	A4	27	19%	45	32%	68	49%	31	23%	47	35%	55	41%
	A5	36	26%	46	33%	58	41%	26	20%	49	37%	58	44%
	A6	44	31%	51	36%	45	32%	19	14%	53	40%	61	46%
	A7	93	66%	22	16%	25	18%	62	47%	44	33%	27	20%
	A8	114	81%	13	9%	13	9%	87	65%	25	19%	21	16%
	A9	113	81%	16	11%	11	8%	76	57%	37	28%	20	15%
	A10	73	52%	38	27%	29	21%	71	53%	31	23%	31	23%

Source: Authors' own research.

Table 3. Comparison of student and worker in homes for older people ratings in the B domain *Assistive role of the robot.*

Domain	Area	Students						Workers in homes for older people					
		I agree		I neither agree or disagree		I disagree		I agree		I neither agree nor disagree		I disagree	
		n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Assistive role of the robot	B1	98	70%	25	18%	17	12%	84	63%	21	16%	28	21%
	B2	120	86%	12	9%	8	6%	92	69%	22	17%	19	14%
	B3	111	79%	20	14%	9	6%	79	59%	38	29%	16	12%
	B4	85	61%	30	21%	25	18%	61	46%	42	32%	30	23%
	B5	101	72%	17	12%	22	16%	74	56%	34	26%	25	19%
	B6	108	77%	15	11%	17	12%	73	55%	34	26%	26	20%
	B7	89	64%	29	21%	22	16%	70	53%	29	22%	34	26%
	B8	111	79%	15	11%	14	10%	76	57%	36	27%	21	16%
	B9	121	86%	7	5%	12	9%	86	65%	20	15%	27	20%
	B10	109	78%	14	10%	17	12%	83	62%	30	23%	20	15%
	B11	96	69%	29	21%	15	11%	81	61%	32	24%	20	15%
	B12	124	89%	7	5%	9	6%	110	83%	13	10%	10	8%
	B13	99	71%	23	16%	18	13%	97	73%	19	14%	17	13%

Source: Authors' own research.

Within the quantitative analysis, we compared the views of students of social work and workers in homes for older people on the potential use of social robots for older adults. In the interviews, we focused on their emotions, opinions, perceived benefits and barriers to the use-potential

Table 4. Comparison of student and worker in homes for older people ratings in the C domain *Social aspects of using the robot.*

Domain	Area	Students						Workers in homes for older people					
		I agree		I neither agree nor disagree		I disagree		I agree		I neither agree nor disagree		I disagree	
		n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Social aspects of using the robot	C1	113	81%	15	11%	12	9%	96	72%	20	15%	17	13%
	C2	102	73%	22	16%	16	11%	85	64%	29	22%	19	14%
	C3	94	67%	26	19%	20	14%	83	62%	34	26%	16	12%
	C4	114	81%	15	11%	11	8%	99	74%	21	16%	13	10%
	C5	73	52%	39	28%	28	20%	70	53%	39	29%	24	18%
	C6	88	63%	31	22%	21	15%	62	47%	44	33%	27	20%

Source: Authors' own research.

Table 5. Comparison of student and worker in homes for older people ratings in the D domain *Ethical issues.*

Domain	Area	Students						Workers in homes for older people					
		I agree		I neither agree nor disagree		I disagree		I agree		I neither agree nor disagree		I disagree	
		n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Ethical issues	D1	102	73%	23	16%	15	11%	86	65%	30	23%	17	13%
	D2	108	77%	22	16%	10	7%	83	62%	26	20%	24	18%
	D3	80	57%	32	23%	28	20%	63	47%	34	26%	36	27%
	D4	117	84%	16	11%	7	5%	97	73%	17	13%	19	14%
	D5	59	42%	39	28%	42	30%	36	27%	50	38%	47	35%

Source: Authors' own research.

of robots. In the analysis, we use the acronym SWx to indicate the statement by the social worker followed by his/her number. FGx denotes the statement of the student participating in the focus group and his/her number. The study was approved by an ethics committee at the University of XXX.

Both groups, the students and workers in homes for older people were informed about the research intent, voluntary participation in the research, anonymity, confidentiality of the researchers and gave their consent to participate in the interview. The interview recording was recorded and then transcribed verbatim and analysed using deductive thematic analysis procedures by [Braun and Clarke \(2012\)](#).

Analysis and results

Table 1 shows a ranking of the items by the percentage of agreement (rating on a scale: 1 and 2) with the statements in A–D domains of UNRAQ. High level of agreement (agreement with an item above 70%) is displayed in bold in the table. In the interpretation, we further focus on the differences amongst students and workers in homes for older people by the percentage of agreement above 10 percent (shown in grey in the table). For items where we observed a difference of less than 10 percent, workers in homes for older people were slightly more likely to agree with the statements.

We also present in **Tables 2–5** a comparison of domains A–D from the perspective of both students and workers in homes for older people. These tables show the comparisons by item in the questionnaire, with scales 1 + 2 (agreement), 4 + 5 (disagreement) merged, and scale 3 (neither agreement nor disagreement) retained. The comparisons were made using SPSS software, which provided us with a descriptive description for each construct in the questionnaire. The comparison clearly shows that students compared to workers identify significantly more with the robot concept presented by the questionnaire items. High levels of agreement with the statements (over 70%) in A–D domains are indicated in grey in the tables.

In the Interaction with the robot and technical issues domain, there were (see **Table 1**) significant differences in the level of agreement between students and workers on two statements (A8, A1). Despite the fact that both students and workers in homes for older people considered *The robot should be adapted to older adults' individual preferences and needs* (A8) to be the most important statement, a significantly lower level of agreement was observed for this statement among workers (by 18%). Eighty-one percent of students and 65 percent of workers agreed with this statement.

Students developed divergent opinions on one statement in the A domain, that is Interaction with the robot and technical issues: *The robot should be adapted to older adults' individual preferences and needs* (A8). We did not observe any significant differences among workers in the A domain, that is Interaction with the robot and technical issues. Workers in homes for older people did not show any significant agreement with any of the statements in the above domain (agreement was less than 70% for all items). The workers were more sceptical about the possible use of robots. According to workers, older adults have some priority needs that cannot be provided by technology. As one social worker stated, '*They just need the human contact... the words... the robot hands are different, I would be concerned if those people would want that (SPI7)*'. Furthermore, according to both students (81%) and staff working in homes for older people (57%) *an older adult should be able to*

select the functions they want to use with the robot and deactivate other functions (A9). For the use of social robots in social work practice, according to both groups of respondents, it is important that social robots have the functions that older adults need and can respond to their individual needs. This is consistent with the research by [Amabili et al. \(2023\)](#) who note that robot users require personalized functions in order to use the robot.

Personalization is a key factor in the effective adoption of gerontechnology. To support this process, social workers need targeted education in human-technology interaction, gerontechnology, and the ethical implications of AI. These areas remain insufficiently addressed in current curricula, underscoring the need for their inclusion in both initial training and ongoing professional development.

We also found significantly lower levels of agreement for the statement: *A robot should be a companion for older adults (A1)* among workers in homes for older people (11%) than among students (see [Table 1](#)). Workers did not dismiss the possibility of a robot as a companion but talked about this possibility in relation to the lack of staffing capacity in the home and the low prestige of working with older people: *'The robot as a companion could be a great asset given the shortage of staff. If it could play chess or cards, why not. Let there be someone like that... (SW13)'*. Nevertheless, and also according to the students, the robot should only be taken as a [supplement](#) or extra help, but not as the main solution to the low emotional support of older adults. Students said, *'Using robots is a wonderful opportunity, but in social services, human contact is better. I think the main source of help should be other people (FG9)'*.

In the Assistive role domain, according to [Table 1](#), there were significant variations in the level of agreement between students and care workers in four statements. The greatest difference was noted in the following statement: *'The robot should monitor the environment (e.g. temperature, humidity) and suggest adequate heating/air conditioning or windows opening (B5)'*. Seventeen percent more students compared to care workers agreed with this statement. Students also more strongly agreed with statements related to assistance with older adult eating such as *B10: The robot should remind older adult of meal and drink times (15%)*, *B4: The robot should provide advice on a healthy diet (15%)* and *B7: The robot should monitor food and fluid intake of older adult (11%)*. The students suggested that in practice this could look like the robot would come and say *'It's time for a drink, tell what the date is, and then it would leave when it sees that an older adult has had a drink (FG10)'*.

The [Table 3](#) shows that students compared to workers identify significantly more with the concept of robot in the B Domain: Assistive role. Whereas students agreed with ten items, workers agreed with only two items (over 70% agreement). According to students, a robot could be

used in social services for older adults, especially in ensuring safety; the robot would call for help in case of an emergency. At the same time, in this domain, we identified groups with different opinions on most of the statements related to assistance in daily activities. Students disagreed on whether the robot should help older adults to maintain memory (B2), provide advice on healthy eating (B3), monitor the environment (B4), measure physiological functions (B5), monitor food and fluid intake (B6), remind of medication doses (B8), remind meal and drinking times (B9), and help find lost items (B12). Also, within the focus group (FG), we observed diverse opinions among students regarding the possible use of robots for older adults. One student stated, *'The robot should only be taken as a supplement or extra help, but not the main solution to the problem. I think the main source of help should be other people'*. In FG, students listed other possible uses of technology in providing assistance to older adults: *'Maybe some voice control device or some text reader would be enough for older adults... For example, smart glasses with a mounted camera. Depending on what older adults focus their gaze on, the camera will comment on it (FG12)'*.

Groups with contrasting views emerged among workers on two statements of the robot's assistive role. The workers did not agree with one another when it came to the statements such as *The robot should increase the security of the older adult's home (B1)* and *The robot should monitor food and fluid intake of the older adult (B7)*. The interviews revealed that only some of the workers were open to the adoption of robots in homes for older people. *'I can't imagine a robot to be used to communicate with older adults. It might vary from client to client; some might prefer it over staying alone in a room... (SP15)'*. According to the workers, social robots could assist with routine activities, for example, *'picking up dishes and washing them up. Then the workers would have more time for the clients. Not the other way around—that the robot would spend time with the client and the worker would do routine activities (SP19)'*. Furthermore, workers said that robots could be used to support older adults in the area of mobility, *'for example with walking—the robot would practise walking or exercise with the person. They would be no need to use a walker as the robot would replace this aid (SP19)'*. In the area of self-care, the workers were not entirely confident about the adoption of robots, *'If older adults accepted it, its assistance would be a relief for the workers. But I don't know... because such assistance is also based on the fact that the workers know the clients and know what to say to them when something goes wrong or how to respond to some of the clients' fears and complaints (SP17)'*. Moreover, the workers believed that robots could be a useful support tool for social contact and retaining of cognitive functions for older adults.

Workers in homes for older people reported high levels of agreement on only two statements (over 70% agreement with the statements) *The*

robot should call for help in case of emergency (B12) and *The robot should help the older adult to find lost objects (B13)*. Smarr et al. (2014) found in their research that older adults prefer a robot over human assistance for tasks related to housework, handling objects, and providing information. In contrast, for tasks related to personal care and leisure activities, they preferred human assistance over a robot. Also in our research, it became clear that from the workers' point of view, a robot is not suitable for older adults in the assistive role: *'I can't imagine that a caregiver and a robot will go together to see an older adult to help them with their personal hygiene. I don't know about that (SW11)'*.

The differing attitudes between students and practitioners may reflect generational and educational gaps. Although students often showed openness toward robotic technologies, they also reported uncertainty and lack of preparation for practical application. These findings highlight the need to integrate gerontechnology into social work education, including not only technical literacy but also ethical evaluation, interdisciplinary collaboration, and reflection on professional values.

According to the comparison in the Social aspects of using the robot domain, according to Table 1, there was a variation in the level of agreement between students and workers only in Area C6: *The robot should accompany the older adult in daily activities (e.g. watching TV, preparing meals)*. Sixteen percent more students than workers agreed with this statement. Within FG, students reported, *'A robot would be most useful to help older adults with anything during the day—for example, getting out of bed, accompanying them somewhere... that would definitely make their life easier (FG1)'*.

In the Social aspects of using the robot domain, students and workers most strongly agreed with the statement (over 70% agreement) *The robot should reduce the feeling of loneliness and improve the mood of the older adult (C1)*, and with the statement *The robot should have entertainment functions (C4)*. Students were not unanimous on whether the robot should help reduce loneliness and whether it should have entertainment functions. In addition, students in this domain agreed with the statement *'The robot should encourage the older adult to contact friends (C2)'*. Students reported that the benefits of social robots included their potential use in preventing loneliness in older adults: *'Older adults tend to be lonely. These days are hectic, and families often lack time ... it's terrible, but I guess that's why robots are being developed... It's convenient if they can talk to a robot and not feel so lonely (FG9)'*. Workers also came up with examples where a robot could help reduce feelings of loneliness: *'If I picture a person who is alone and an introvert, a robot could reduce anxiety for that person. Equally, if someone is used to have contact and people around them, then for that person the technology in the sense of a robot could be useful... it depends on how we assess the needs of the person (SW10)'*.

Some workers saw a possible use of the robot in the social area: *‘I can imagine it more in the social area; that it would read something or have a chat with... so, they would feel that interest that someone’s there... and someone’s communicating with them (SW1)’*. Another social worker accounted, *‘That’s a great idea because I sometimes feel like I need to split myself into pieces in order to get everything done in a day (activation worker, SW10)’*. Similarly, in [Van Assche et al.’s \(2023\)](#) research, social robots are a promising solution when it comes to alleviating feelings of loneliness and social isolation.

These responses highlight a core aim of social work with older adults: reducing social isolation and fostering inclusion. Social robots may support this goal by enhancing quality of life and dignity, but their use must remain person-centred and based on individual needs—not just on technological possibilities.

Social work education must prepare students not only to understand how social robots function but also to critically evaluate their appropriateness, plan their ethical and effective integration into care plans, and engage in interdisciplinary collaboration with developers, healthcare providers, and families. We therefore argue for the integration of gerontechnology and digital literacy modules into social work curricula, with a focus on: (1) psychosocial and emotional impacts of technology use; (2) ethical dilemmas in digital care; (3) methods for assessing social needs and matching them with appropriate technological tools; (4) and participatory approaches that include older adults in decision-making processes.

A comparison of the results of students and workers in homes for older people on the Ethical issues domain ([Table 1](#)) showed that 15 percent more students than workers agreed with the two statements: *D5 It is acceptable for the robot to have a large amount of information about the older adult (e.g. social, medical, and other information)* and *D2 The older adult should be able to send the robot to its place (docking station) and asked it to stay there*. Furthermore, 11 percent more students than workers agreed to the following statement: *D4 The older adult should be able to shut off the robot in specific situations (e.g. friends visiting and for other privacy related reasons)*. With the statement: *D3 It is acceptable for the robot to inform a family member or caregiver about the older adult’s behaviour or health problems*, agreed 10 percent more students than workers. Again, students were more likely to agree with statements in the D domain *Ethical Issues* (see [Table 5](#)) compared to workers. Not all students agreed with the use of robots: *‘It is risky to use robots in social work. Robots can fail, meaning that someone would have to check on them regularly (FG4)’*.

The workers disagreed on the statement stressing the robot’s ethical role: *The older adult should be in control of the robot (D1)* and the statement *The older adult should be able to send the robot to its place*

(docking station) and asked it to stay there (D2). As stated by one worker, *'It's beating up on me a little bit in terms of ethics because a lot of questions in the questionnaire... I was like oh well be careful here, that's borderline ethical (SW17)'*. The use of social robots brings a number of ethical considerations to social work. According to Bradwell et al. (2020), researchers should focus on topics such as deception, infantilisation, and the threat of limited human contact at the expense of robot contact. These topics were also reported by students and workers. We did not observe any differences of opinion among students in this domain.

According to both students and social workers, the most important robot function in this domain is to turn it off in specific situations requiring privacy (D4). The issue of privacy is also key in other research studies (for example, Irfan, Kuoppamäki, and Skantze 2024). Focus group results showed that students shared similar concerns, *'I would worry about someone hacking the system and maybe misusing the data. Someone could secretly look at it... (FG7)'*. The issue of privacy is important, according to students and social workers, to maintain a sense of safety and security when using any technology.

Students talked about the need for education in gerontechnology. This finding may be related to the fact that courses that prepare social workers in gerontechnology are not commonly included in the curriculum for training of future social workers in universities. As stated by one student, *'A social worker should direct older adults or their families to some place that will give them advice. We also don't have a background in technology and it's new in social work... A social worker probably won't know all the technology and it works, but they should direct a person to where they can provide them with the information (FG2)'*. Otherwise, the 'robotics divide' that López Peláez (2014) writes about may occur.

Social workers also reported that they had no experience in using social robots and lacked knowledge: *'If something was to be introduced, there would need to be some training for the workers so that they could try out a robot... because us who are not experts, if all we get is instructions it's difficult... (SW16)'*. It has previously been found that social workers lack digital competencies (Kalenda and Kowaliková 2020).

These findings highlight the urgent need to integrate technological and ethical training into social work education. This could include: (1) dedicated courses on gerontechnology and ethical decision-making in the context of digital care; (2) interdisciplinary learning involving social work, health, ethics, and information technology; (3) opportunities for experiential learning, such as simulations or workshops involving real robotic devices; (4) critical reflection on how technology intersects with core social work values like autonomy, dignity, participation, and justice.

Incorporating such training into university curricula and professional development programmes can empower both students and current

practitioners to make informed, ethical, and value-driven decisions about the use of social robots in practice. As Technological Gerontological Education (TGE) continues to develop as a field (Barrera-Algarín, Sarasola-Sánchez-Serrano, and Sarasola-Fernández 2023), it presents a timely opportunity to enhance social work's capacity to navigate the technological transformations shaping care for older adults.

Discussion and conclusion

Given the fact that expert studies on the use of social robots in social work practice, specifically in residential social services for older adults, have not yet captured the full breadth of social reality, we believe that our results can broaden this perspective. We found only studies from China (Lei et al. 2024) and South Korea (Lee and Shin 2024; Shin and Lee 2024).

The research results showed that students of social work agreed to a higher extent with the items in each domain of UNRAQ compared to workers in homes for older people. Students think that social robots offer a number of functions that they believe older adults could use. Both groups agreed that a robot would be useful if it was able to call for help for an older adult in an emergency. Some students and workers further agreed that in the social area, a robot could help prevent loneliness in older adults. For other functions offered by robots, students and workers in homes for older people were not unanimous. We assume that social workers and care workers have a clearer understanding of current technological difficulties and limitations compared to students (Share and Pender 2018). However, students seem to have a more open attitude toward the technology, often focusing on its symbolic value in terms of self-identity (Zsiga et al. 2013). Peek et al. (2014) pointed out that effective implementation of robotic solutions depends on care workers' understanding of a robot's functionality, its necessity, and their perceptions of its benefits and risks. Furthermore, professionals' confidence in the robots' ability to learn and use care robots also influences their willingness to adopt robotic technologies in practice (Rantanen et al. 2018).

This study contributes to the growing but still limited body of knowledge on the acceptance and perceived usefulness of social robots in social work practice, particularly within residential care services for older adults. Our findings highlight important differences in the attitudes of future social workers (students) and current social workers and care workers, which reflect broader debates in gerontological social work about the role of technology in care provision.

Importantly, both groups recognized the potential role of robots in emergency assistance. Also, both groups see a potential role in mitigating loneliness, similarly as in cited literature where technology can

complement human care (Rantanen et al. 2018). Nevertheless, there remains a clear ambivalence, especially among social workers and care workers, regarding the broader social and emotional capacities of robots, reflecting enduring skepticism within gerontological social work about substituting human relationships with technological proxies.

In Poland, similar research has been conducted among medical students. According to the medical students, the robot could remind older adults to take their medication regularly, ensure their safety, monitor their health and environment, provide cognitive training and encourage them to stay physically fit and active (Kropińska et al. 2020). The above results partially correspond with our findings, where existing and future workers in social work organisations prefer, according to their accounts, the assistive function of robots to their social and emotional support.

According to Kropińska et al. (2020), health care students have a positive attitude toward social robots, which may also influence their acceptance among older adults. In the future, health care professionals and also social workers could help older adults to choose the right robots (with necessary functions) that best suit their needs. However, this would require expanding the curriculum to include gerontechnology in universities preparing social and health care workers. As Barrera-Algarín, Sarasola-Sánchez-Serrano, and Sarasola-Fernández (2023) argue from within gerontological education we can now see development of technological gerontological education as a new professional area in the field of social work. Technological Gerontological Education (TGE) proves a key element in the development of the capabilities and integration of older adults as active contributors to and direct beneficiaries of technologies.

These conclusions correspond with the findings of our research, where the future use of gerontotechnologies in the field of social services for the target group of older adults should positively influence their acceptance, not only by the users themselves, but especially by service providers, i.e. social and other interested workers. In this context, there is a need to provide training for future and existing workers that reflects their cultural and socio-demographic specificities.

From a practice perspective, these findings suggest that while technological solutions may offer new tools, their adoption in social work requires careful alignment with professional values, ethical considerations, and service users' needs. Social workers and care workers reservations underline the importance of realistic communication about technological capabilities and the necessity of involving frontline staff in decisions about technology adoption to enhance trust and acceptance older adults.

In terms of research, our findings reinforce the need for further, context-sensitive studies exploring the cultural, organizational, and individual factors influencing technology acceptance in social work settings.

Comparative studies across countries and care models could offer valuable insights into how socio-cultural norms shape attitudes toward gerontechnology.

Finally, for service users and family carers, the gradual integration of robots into care must be approached inclusively and ethically. Both groups need to be actively involved in discussions about how these technologies might support—not replace—human care relationships. Training and initiatives for family carers may help them accept technology.

Supplementary data

[Supplementary data](#) is available at *British Journal of Social Work* online.

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